

A 0.3-V 62-dB Bulk-Driven OTA with Hybrid Frequency Compensation in 65 nm CMOS

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a novel 65-nm CMOS ultra-low-voltage (ULV) operational transconductance amplifier (OTA) design. The proposed architecture integrates partial positive feedback (PPF) with a hybrid frequency compensation technique that combines current-buffer and Miller compensation approaches. This hybrid compensation effectively mitigates the primary limitation of PPF-based OTAs i.e. their sensitivity to transistor mismatch. Operating at a supply voltage of 0.3 V and consuming just 23.7 nW of power, the two-stage OTA achieves a rail-to-rail input common-mode range, a DC voltage gain of 61.7 dB, and a gain-bandwidth product of 12.7 kHz with a 20-pF load capacitance.

KEY WORDS: Operational Amplifier, Operational Transconductance Amplifier, Bulk-driven, Low voltage, Low power.

1. Introduction

In recent years a number of ultra-low-voltage (ULV) and ultra-low-power (ULP) operational transconductance amplifiers (OTAs) with supply voltages of 0.5 V and lower have been reported in literature [1-22]. Most of the designs were realized using a relatively old 0.18 μm technology. However, as technological dimensions decrease, achieving good parameters

of OTAs becomes more and more difficult. First of all this refers to such parameters as voltage gain, common-mode rejection (CMRR) and power supply rejection (PSRR) ratios. This is associated with lower intrinsic voltage gains of MOS transistors in deeply scaled technologies, as well as with lower bulk to gate transconductance ratio, that further lowers intrinsic voltage gains of bulk-driven (BD) transistors, usually used in input stages of ULV amplifiers. For example, implementing the OTA design from [7] in a 65-nm technology node would result in approximately 20 dB reduction in voltage gain compared to the original 0.18 μm design, highlighting the significant impact of technology scaling on OTA performance.

The voltage gain of ULV amplifiers can be increased using more gain stages, [4], [8], or applying one of the existing gain boosting techniques, like for example the partial positive feedback (PPF) technique [3], [12]. However, both approaches have their own limitations. One of the most significant drawbacks of the PPF technique is its increased sensitivity to transistor mismatch which can degrade the phase margin (PM), and generally complicates frequency compensation of OTA. This sensitivity imposes practical constraints on the depth of positive feedback that can be applied. As a result, the achievable improvement in voltage gain is limited,

In this work a new approach to design of sub 0.5-V, sub 100-nm OTAs is presented. The proposed two-stage structure, is based on a BD non-tailed differential pair, and combines the PPF technique with a hybrid frequency compensation circuit, which can be seen as a combination of a current buffer [23], [24] and classic Miller compensation techniques. It was shown that, both, the gain-bandwidth product (GBW) as well as the PM of the amplifier are much less sensitive to transistor mismatch in this case, compared to classic solutions, which simplifies frequency compensation and improves stability in the presence of mismatch. This allows increasing the depth of PPF, thus achieving the DC voltage gain of the two-stage OTA above 60 dB using deeply scaled technology (65nm), while not compromising or even improving its small-signal power efficiency as compared with state of the art.

The proposed OTA can serve as a basic building block in analog parts of ULV and ULP systems, realized in deeply-scaled technologies, in such applications as autonomous nodes of sensor networks, biomedical implants or wearable biomedical systems.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the new OTA, and its theoretical analysis. Section III presents a design procedure, Section IV shows the results of simulations and measurements of the fabricated structure. and compares this work with state of the art. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

2. Circuit description

The CMOS schematic of the proposed two-stage ULV OTA is shown in Fig.1. It combines a BD non-tailed input stage with PPF (M_1 - M_5) [6], [25] and a pseudo-class AB output stage with an additional feedforward path (M_6 - M_9) [7]. Due to the BD non-tailed architecture the circuit can operate with very low supply voltages, while offering rail-to-rail input common-mode range.

The input stage can be seen as a non-tailed differential amplifier with PPF generated by the cross-coupled pair M_{3A} - M_{3B} . The transistors M_3 generate negative conductances ($-g_{m3}$), that decrease the total conductance at the drain/gate nodes of M_2 , equal to $g_{m2}+g_{ds2}+g_{ds3}+g_{ds5}-g_{m3}$.

Decreasing the resulting conductance at the drains of M_2 leads to increasing the voltage gain of the first stage, but also to increasing the resulting sensitivity of the first stage to transistor mismatch [25]. This leads to a tradeoff between circuit sensitivity and voltage gain improvement, and is one of the most important drawbacks of the PPF technique.

Fig.1. CMOS schematic of the proposed OTA with hybrid frequency compensation.

Fig.2. Block diagram of the proposed OTA.

The current mirrors M_4 - M_6 and M_6 - M_8 form a feedforward path with the current gain K , used to cancel the RHP zero from the compensation capacitance C_C . At the same time, the transistor M_8 sources its drain current to the load, thus, together with transistor M_9 , forms a pseudo-class AB output stage. In addition, the above mentioned feedforward path, further improves the CMRR of the OTA.

The capacitances C_K and C_C are used for frequency compensation. The compensation network is a superposition of two networks. The capacitance C_K provides frequency compensation using the so-called current buffer method [23], [24], while C_C is used in a classic Miller compensation circuit. As it will be shown, such a hybrid approach leads to a decreased sensitivity of the structure to transistor mismatch, namely, eliminates the most important drawback of the PPF technique and allows achieving higher voltage gains than conventional solutions.

2.1. AC Performance

The block diagram of the amplifier, used for AC analysis, is shown in Fig.2. where g_{o1} and g_{o2} denote the output conductance of the first and the second stage respectively, C_{o1} is the output capacitance of the first stage, C_L is the load capacitance (includes the output capacitance of the second stage C_{o2}), $g_A = g_{m2} + g_{ds2} + g_{ds3} + g_{ds5} - g_{m3}$ is the conductance at node A, and C_A is the sum of the parasitic capacitances associated with this node. The transconductance $g_{mbA} = g_{mb2} + g_{mb3}$. The current gain K of the feedforward path is given by: $K = (W/L)_6(W/L)_8 / (W/L)_4(W/L)_7$.

Based on AC analysis of the circuit in Fig.2, the voltage gain of the OTA can be expressed in the form:

$$A_v \cong A_{vo} \frac{\left(1 + s \frac{C_K + C_A}{2g_{m9}}\right) \left(1 + s \frac{(K-1)C_C + K C_{o1}}{g_{m9}}\right) \left(1 + s \frac{C_K + C_A}{g_A}\right)}{\frac{1}{\omega_o^2} \left(1 + \frac{s}{\omega_d}\right) \left(s^2 + s \frac{\omega_o}{Q} + \omega_o^2\right) \left(1 + s \frac{C_K + C_A}{g_A}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where, neglecting the small impact of the feedforward path M_6 - M_8 , the DC voltage gain A_{vo} can be approximated as:

$$A_{vo} \cong \frac{2g_{mb1}}{(1+p-m)} \frac{g_{m9}}{g_{o1}g_{o2}} \quad (2)$$

with $m=g_{m3}/g_{m2}$ and $p=(g_{ds2}+g_{ds3}+g_{ds5})/g_{m2}$. Note, that A_{vo} increases as m tends to $(1+p)$, i.e. as the PPF depth increases. Unfortunately this is associated with increased sensitivity of the transconductance of the first stage to the parameter m , caused by transistor mismatch-

From (1) we can also conclude, that the parasitic pole associated with PPF ($g_A/(C_K+C_A)$) is in the proposed configuration cancelled by a zero, located at the same frequency. Therefore, even at very low value of $g_A=g_{m2}(1+p-m)$, caused by increased depth of PPF, when $1+p-m$ tends to zero, this pole does not limit frequency response of OTA in a direct way, and the voltage gain of the OTA simplifies to:

$$A_v \cong A_{vo} \frac{\left(1+s \frac{C_K+C_A}{2g_{m9}}\right) \left(1+s \frac{(K-1)C_C+K C_{o1}}{g_{m9}}\right)}{\left(1+\frac{s}{\omega_d}\right) \left(s^2+s \frac{\omega_o}{Q}+\omega_o^2\right) \frac{1}{\omega_o^2}} \quad (3)$$

The frequency of the dominant pole of (3), ω_d , for $g_{o1} \ll g_A$ and $C_C \ll C_L$ can be approximated as:

$$\omega_d \cong \frac{g_{o1}}{C_C \left(1+\frac{g_{m9}}{g_{o2}}\right) + C_K \frac{g_{m1} g_{m9}}{g_A g_{o2}}} \quad (4)$$

Thus, the GBW product of the OTA is:

$$GBW = \omega_d A_{vo} \cong \frac{2g_{mb1}}{(1+p-m) \left(C_C + C_K \frac{g_{m1}}{g_A}\right)} \quad (5)$$

However, with $g_A=g_{m2}(1+p-m)$, and $C_C \ll C_K(g_{m1}/g_A)$, this parameter can be approximated as:

$$GBW \cong \frac{2g_{mb1}}{C_K \frac{g_{m1}}{g_{m2}}} \quad (6)$$

Thus, the GBW product does not depend on the coefficient m (g_{m3}/g_{m2} ratio), which is a considerable advantage of the proposed structure, and allows achieving very low values of the expression $(1+p-m)$, i.e. increasing the depth of PPF and consequently the DC voltage gain of the OTA, with reasonable sensitivity of the structure to transistors mismatch.

For moderate and low values of C_L , the coefficients ω_o and Q referring to non-dominant poles can be approximated as:

$$\omega_o \cong \sqrt{\frac{g_{m1} g_{m9}}{(C_{o1}+C_C)C_L}} \quad (7)$$

$$Q \cong \sqrt{\frac{g_{m1}g_{m9}}{g_A^2} \cdot \frac{C_K^2}{(C_{o1}+C_C)C_L}} = \frac{\omega_o}{\omega_A} \quad (8)$$

where $\omega_A = g_A/C_K = g_{m2}(1+p-m)/C_K$.

The quality factor of the non-dominant poles Q increases, as C_L decreases, and can achieve relatively high values, resulting in gain peaking. Thus, the second compensation loop, with capacitance C_C , allows limiting the value of Q , especially for low C_L , thus avoiding this undesirable effect, which could limit stability margin or even cause instability of the OTA. Also note, that Q increases with lowering the conductance $g_A = g_{m2}(1+p-m)$, i.e. increasing the depth of PPF for larger dc gain. To maintain a sufficiently low value of Q , to avoid gain peaking and amplitude margin reduction, the value of ω_o must be decreased, which can be achieved with increasing C_C . Thus, the decreasing value of g_A however limits the value of ω_o , and consequently the GBW product of OTA.

The zeros of (3) are typically located at much higher frequencies than ω_o , due to the relatively large value of g_{m9} .

2.2. CMRR Performance

The non-tailed input stage with PPF provides acceptable CMRR performance, comparable to the one of the classical BD differential pair. However, the additional feedforward path M_6 - M_8 further increases the CMRR. Considering the relatively low intrinsic voltage gains of MOS transistors in nanometer technologies, this is a valuable property of the proposed structure.

The small-signal equivalent schematic of the OTA used for calculating its dc common-mode (CM) gain is shown in Fig. 3, where $g_B = g_{m2} + g_{m3} + g_{ds2} + g_{ds3} + g_{ds5}$, $g_{o7} = g_{ds6} + g_{ds7}$ and the other symbols have been defined previously.

Fig.3. Small-signal equivalent schematic for calculating the common-mode dc voltage gain.

From Fig. 3, assuming $(g_{mb2}+g_{mb3})/(g_{m2}+g_{m3}) = g_{mb1}/g_{m1}$, the common-mode gain of the OTA, A_{vcm} , can be calculated as:

$$A_{vcm} = \frac{g_{m9}}{g_{o2}} \left[1 - \frac{g_{m8}}{g_{m9}} \cdot \frac{g_{m6}}{g_{m7}+g_{ds6}+g_{ds7}} \right] \cdot A_{cm1} \quad (9)$$

where A_{cm1} can be considered as a CM gain of the input stage, given by:

$$A_{cm1} = \frac{g_{mb1}}{g_{o1}} \left(\frac{g_{ds2}+g_{ds3}+g_{ds5}}{g_{m2}+g_{m3}+g_{ds2}+g_{ds3}+g_{ds5}} \right) \left(\frac{g_{o1}}{g_{m4}+g_{o1}} \right) \quad (10)$$

From (8), (9) and (2), assuming $g_{m8}/g_{m9}=g_{m7}/g_{m6}$, the dc CMRR of the OTA can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & CMRR \\ &= \frac{2}{(1+p-m)} \left(\frac{g_{m2} + g_{m3} + g_{ds2} + g_{ds3} + g_{ds5}}{g_{ds2} + g_{ds3} + g_{ds5}} \right) \left(\frac{g_{m4} + g_{o1}}{g_{o1}} \right) \left(\frac{g_{m7} + g_{ds6} + g_{ds7}}{g_{ds6} + g_{ds7}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

From (11), the PPF increases the CMRR, since it increases the differential voltage gain, while it not affects the CM gain.

In addition, the feedforward path M_6 - M_8 further increases the CMRR, which is expressed by the last factor of (11). This effect can be intuitively explained as follows. Variations of the input CM voltage cause small variations of the drain currents of $M_{1A,B}$. Assume I_{D1A} , I_{D1B} are increasing. Thanks to the feedforward path this entails increasing of I_{D8} . However, I_{D9} is increasing as well, due to the fact, that the current gain of the current mirror M_{4A} , M_{4B} is less than unity, and the potential at the gate of M_9 is increasing. Since both, I_{D8} as well as I_{D9} increase, they compensate each other, thus decreasing the resulting CM gain, even though, due to the impact of $g_{ds6}+g_{ds7}$, this compensation is not ideal.

As it can be concluded from (11), the resulting CMRR is of the order of the voltage gain of a three-stage amplifier, further increased by PPF. Thus, even for nanometer technologies this parameter can achieve around 100 dB, which significantly outperforms the results for most ULV OTAs. Also note, that due to the large transistor channel areas, this parameter remains very high even in the presence of mismatch.

2.3. Input-referred noise

The input referred noise of the OTA is determined by noise properties of its input stage, and was already analyzed in other works. The input referred noise spectral density, in weak inversion, can be expressed as [25]:

$$\overline{v_{in}^2} = N \left[\frac{8kT}{3g_{mb1}^2} (g_{m1} + g_{m4}) + \frac{1}{g_{mb1}^2 f C_{OX}} \left(\frac{K_p g_{m1}^2}{W_1 L_1} + \frac{K_n g_{m4}^2}{W_4 L_4} \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

where:

$$N = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{n}{(1+p/2)^2} \left[1 + m + \frac{(1-m+p)^2}{n} \right] \quad (13)$$

where $n=g_{m1}/g_{m2}$, k is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, K_p and K_n are the flicker noise constants for p- and n-channel MOS transistors respectively, and C_{OX} is the oxide capacitance per unit area.

The input referred noise is approximately equal to the input noise of a classical BD differential stage, biased with the same total current, and with the same sum of transistor channel areas, and slightly decreases with decreasing the difference $(1-m+p)$.

2.4. Large-signal performance

For large amplitudes of the input step and $C_K \ll C_L$, the positive and negative slew-rate (SR) can be estimated as:

$$SR_+ = \min \left(\frac{K \cdot I_{D1max}}{C_L}; V_{DD} \frac{g_A}{C_K + C_A} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$SR_- = \frac{I_{D1max}}{C_c} \quad (15)$$

where I_{D1max} is the maximum value of I_{D1} for the given input step $|V_{in}|$, which for large input steps (approaching V_{DD}) can be estimated as:

$$I_{D1max} \approx I_B \exp \left((n_p - 1) \frac{|V_{in}|}{n_p U_T} \right) \quad (16)$$

where n_p is the subthreshold slope factor for a p-channel MOS and U_T is the thermal potential. The second factor in (14) represents impact of the time constant associated with the drain/gate node of M_{2A} .

To ensure signal fidelity, the minimum required SR, which is equal to the minimum of the two SR_+ and SR_- , is usually defined by:

$$SR_{min} = 2\pi \cdot f_{max} \cdot V_{peak} \quad (16)$$

where f_{max} and V_{peak} is the frequency and the amplitude of a sinusoidal signal. Of course based on (16) for a given SR_{min} the maximum frequency for a given V_{peak} or the maximum V_{peak} for a given frequency can be calculated. Exceeding the above limits may result in a gradual increase in the total harmonic distortion (THD).

3. Design procedure

The design has been started with the biasing currents of the input stage, which determines the input thermal noise of OTA, which is a dominant noise component in this design. Assuming $m=0.9$ to maximize the voltage gain, we chose $I_B=I_{D5A}=I_{D5B}=4nA$, that entailed $I_{D2}=2.11nA$ and $I_{D3}=1.89nA$. The biasing current of M_1 , was chosen equal to I_{D2} .

The compensation capacitance C_K was calculated for the assumed GBW of 5.3 kHz, using (6), where $g_{mb2} = (n_p-1)I_{D2}/n_pU_T$.

In the next step, the bias current of M_9 was set. For the assumed $C_L=20pF$, the frequency g_{m9}/C_L was assumed to be ca. $1.8xGBW$ using the formula $I_{D9}=g_{m9}(n_nU_T)$, which gives $I_{D9}/I_{D1}=K=20$. The current gain of the current mirror M_8/M_7 was assumed equal to 10, which resulted in $I_{D7}=2I_{D1}$. The chosen value of $I_{D8,9}/I_{D7}$ allows saving power, while maintaining a sufficiently high value of the parasitic pole associated with M_7 .

The channel lengths (L) of the transistors in the input stage were assumed to be equal to $1\mu m$, that allows increasing their intrinsic voltage gains and entails large channel areas, that decreases both, the input-referred flicker noise, as well as the input-referred offset. The above aspect is not so important in the output stage, however, also here $L=1\mu m$ was assumed to increase the voltage gain. Only for transistors M_7 and M_8 $L=0.4\mu m$ was selected, to decrease the total parasitic capacitance at the gate/drain node of M_7 , i.e. to increase the frequency of the parasitic pole associated with this node much above GBW. All channel widths (W) of the used transistors were determined during the simulation phase in such a way that $|V_{GS}|$ of all

transistors were equal to around mid-supply for the assumed I_D and L . Such a choice allows maximizing a headroom for possible PVT variations and signal swing.

The capacitance C_C has also been finally chosen during the simulation phase, to obtain proper value of the stability margin. By increasing the value of C_C to 0.162pF, we obtained an assumed value of amplitude margin (10dB without load, i.e. in the most critical case) while maintaining PM above 60deg.

4. Simulation and experimental results

4.1. Implementation

The proposed OTA was fabricated using a 65-nm CMOS technology from UMC, with threshold voltages of $V_{THn}=0.414V$, $V_{THp}=-0.325V$. The nominal supply voltage V_{DD} was 0.3 V, however, for the purpose of measurement, a symmetrical voltage supply of $\pm 0.15V$ was used. The microphotograph and layout of the fabricated OTA are shown in Fig.4. The total silicon area is $43.5 \times 57 \mu m^2$. The transistors aspect ratios and other design parameters are shown in Table I.

Fig.4. Microphotograph (a) and layout (b) of the fabricated OTA.

Table I. Transistor aspect ratios and other design parameters.

Device	(W/L) [$\mu m/\mu m$]	Device	(W/L) [$\mu m/\mu m$]
M1, M2	10x1.5/1	M8	160x1.5/0.4
M3	9x1.5/1	M9	120x2/1
M4	6x2/1	Device	value
M5, MB	10x2/1	C_K	0.6pF
M6	12x2/1	C_C	0.162pF
M7	16x1.5/0.4	I_B	4nA

As mentioned previously, the relatively large transistor channel sizes allow improving DC voltage gain and reducing sensitivity to mismatch and flicker noise. As it is known, the technological constants describing sensitivity to mismatch are not proportional to the feature size of CMOS technology. Therefore, transistor sizes in analog circuits realized in deeply scaled technologies often remain relatively large, compared to their feature sizes, to preserve low sensitivity to mismatch. Moreover, as can be seen in Fig.3.b, most of the silicon area in this design is occupied by two compensation capacitors. Therefore, larger transistor sizes do not increase the total chip area in a significant proportion, that allows maintaining a good compromise between silicon area and other design parameters.

4.2. Post-layout simulation

In order to prove some properties of the designed circuit, predicted by theoretical analysis, post-layout simulations have been performed in Cadence environment.

Table II summarizes the simulated parameters of OTA for $I_B=4\text{nA}$, $V_{DD}=0.3\text{V}$ and $C_L=20\text{pF}$. Most of the simulated parameters are close to the ones determined by theoretical formulas. However, the theoretical GBW calculated from (5) was 5.30 kHz, while the simulated value was 8.08 kHz. The larger simulated value was caused by a small peak on magnitude characteristic above GBW, which depends on C_C and was also predicted theoretically.

Table II. Simulated parameters of OTA, $I_B=4\text{nA}$, $V_{DD}=0.3\text{V}$, $C_L=20\text{pF}$.

Parameter	value	Parameter	value
A_{vo}	57.7 dB	SR+	2.69 V/ms
GBW	8.075 kHz	SR-	31.54V/ms
PM	74.03 deg	1 % t_{sett}	260/150 μs
CMRR	88.08 dB	input noise @ 1kHz	4.7 μV
PSRR	50.31 dB	P_{diss}	18.58 nW

Table III shows the results of Monte-Carlo mismatch analysis (200 runs). The results show a relatively low sensitivity of the investigated parameters of OTA to transistor mismatch. However, special attention should be paid to the GBW and PM parameters, which prove low sensitivity of the proposed compensation technique to mismatch, comparable to the sensitivity of classical circuits without PPF.

Table III. Results of Monte Carlo Analysis (200 runs), $C_L=20\text{pF}$.

Parameter	Mean	Std.dev	min	max
A_{vo} , [dB]	57.68	0.736	55.79	59.56
GBW, [kHz]	8.08	0.34	7.24	9.056
PM, [deg]	73.88	2.06	68.2	79.2
CMRR, [dB]	53.79	8.4	38.36	87.06
PSRR, [dB]	48.22	8.46	34.3	68.68
Input offset,[mV]	0.187	6.026	-17.62	16.3
P_{diss} , [nW]	18.6	0.59	16.88	20.36

Table IV shows the results of a standard corner analysis. The results confirm that the design is also resistant to process and temperature (P/T) variations. The systematic input referred offset remains in the range of tens of μV for all cases, and changes by less than $3.1 \mu\text{V}/\text{deg}$ with temperature.

Table IV. Simulated Main Performance Parameters Over Process and Temperature Variations, $C_L=20\text{pF}$.

Parameter (T=27 °C)	SS C_{max}/C_{min}	SF C_{max}/C_{min}	TT C_{max}/C_{min}	FS C_{max}/C_{min}	FF C_{max}/C_{min}	TT corner		
						0°	27°	70°
P_{diss} , [nW]	16.0	18.6	18.58	18.8	22.8	15.87	18.58	25.74
A_{vo} , [dB]	59.55	59.4	57.7	54.6	52.05	60.84	57.7	46.5
GBW, [kHz]	9.6/6.2	8/11.6	8.075	10.1/6	10/5.9	8.08	8.075	7.26
PM, [°]	43/80.3	51/86.5	74.03	53/85.4	67.1/89	69.48	74.03	81.5
CMRR @ DC, [dB]	78.4	93.4	88.1	80.0	91.4	79.48	88	83.1
PSRR @ DC, [dB]	46.7	54.1	50.3	44.8	48	47.9	50.3	43.5

Process corners: S-slow, F-fast, T-typical, first: n-channel MOS, second, p-channel MOS.

Fig.5. shows the open-loop frequency characteristics of the OTA for different C_C , which illustrates impact of the second compensation loop. The quality factor of the non-dominant poles decreases with increasing C_C , as predicted theoretically.

Fig.6 shows the simulated GBW product of the OTA as a function of C_C . The results agree with (4), showing rather limited impact of C_C on GBW. The observed limited impact of C_L results from the assumed approximations. Note that it is lower for larger C_C , because the quality factor given by (8), which has impact on simulated GBW, is also lower. The PM of the OTA decreases with C_C for lower C_L , ($< 20\text{pF}$) which is associated with a decreasing

quality factor of non-dominant poles for larger C_C (it can also be observed in Fig.5) . Even though the PM is larger for smaller C_C , the amplitude margin of OTA decreases in this case, due to the larger quality factor of the non-dominant poles, that results in a peak on magnitude characteristics. To avoid this unwanted effect, C_C in our design was increased to 0.162 pF, to maintain sufficient amplitude margin of 10 dB without load (most critical case), while it was only 2.1 dB without C_C .

Fig.5. Simulated frequency characteristics of OTA for $C_C=0$ pF, 0.2pF and 0.5pF, $C_K=0.6$ pF, $C_L=20$ pF (gain - solid line, phase - dashed line).

(a)

Fig.6. Simulated gain-bandwidth product of OTA (a) and a phase margin (b) as a function of C_C for different C_L , $C_K=0.6$ pF.

Table V. Results of Monte Carlo Analysis (200 runs), for different m , and different compensation schemes, $C_L=20$ pF.

Version	A_{VO} [dB]		GBW [kHz]		PM [deg]	
	Mean	Std.dv	Mean	Std.dv	Mean	Std.dv
$m=0.9$ $C_C=0.162$ pF, $C_K=0.6$ pF	57.7	0.74	8.08	0.34	73.9	2.06
$m=0.9$ (Miller) $C_C=0.4.5$ pF, $C_K=0$ pF	57.6	1.03	4.96	0.39	74.0	4.33
$m=1$ $C_C=0.5$ pF, $C_K=0.6$ pF	65.4	1.52	7.97	0.37	64.9	2.84
$m=1$ (Miller) $C_C=10.3$ pF, $C_K=0$ pF	65.1	2.21	6.62	0.52	65.4	9.56

In order to better demonstrate the advantages of the proposed technique we performed MC mismatch analysis for several versions of the circuit, with the hybrid and classic Miller compensation ($C_K=0$). Besides, each type of compensation was applied in OTAs with different coefficient m , namely 0.9 and 1. The OTA with $m=0.9$ consisted of transistors with W/L shown in Table I, while for $m=1$ $(W/L)_3$ was modified to be equal to $(W/L)_2 = 10 \times 1.5/1$. The capacitances C_C for Miller OTAs were chosen to obtain equal PMs for both compensation schemes and for the given m . The results are shown in Table V.

As can be concluded from Table V, the proposed compensation scheme offers much lower sensitivity to mismatch than classic Miller compensation, and the advantage increases with the increase of the m coefficient. This is due to the fact, that the transconductance of the first stage of the OTA ($g_{m1}=2g_{mb1}/(1+p-m)$) highly depends on transistor mismatch, since its sensitivity to the difference of $1+p-m$ highly increases as m tends to $1+p$. This highly affects

possible variations of GBW and PM of the Miller OTA. In the proposed scheme the sensitivities of GBW and PM to transistor mismatch (especially the relative ones) are much lower, that proves its advantages in structures with PPF. This allows increasing m , thus maximizing voltage gain. Even for $m=1$ the sensitivity to m is comparable to the one obtained in classical structures without PPF, where small variations are mainly due to variations of biasing currents. Notably, the sensitivity of the investigated Miller OTA for $m=1$ is unacceptable in practical designs, with minimum PM falling to ca. 30 deg, with nominal PM of 65.4deg, while for hybrid compensated OTA the minimum PM was ca. 56deg.

The above results prove, that the proposed technique is better suited for frequency compensation of the circuits with PPF, providing lower sensitivity to transistor mismatch, that enables increasing the parameter m and consequently increase the dc voltage gain. In addition, the required total compensation capacitance is lower than the one required in conventional Miller method, thus enabling saving a silicon area.

In the fabricated version, out of caution however, we choose $m=0.9$. The simulated frequency characteristics in the presence of mismatch for the hybrid and Miller compensation with $m=0.9$ (two first rows in Table V) are shown in Fig.7. It is easy to notice the difference in sensitivity of both versions.

For $C_L=0$ the phase and the amplitude margins for the considered OTA were 97.1 deg and 10.0 dB respectively namely, the circuit provided stable operation also in this case.

(a)

(b)

Fig.7. Simulated frequency characteristics of OTA with hybrid (a) and Miller compensation (b) under transistor mismatch, $C_L=20\text{pF}$.

4.3. Experimental results

Fig. 8. shows the open-loop frequency characteristics of OTA, measured using the Bode 100 vector network analyzer, for $I_B=4\text{nA}$, $V_{DD}=0.3\text{V}$, and $C_L=20\text{pF}$. The measured characteristics were approximately consistent with simulations, however, with P_{diss} increased by 27% to 23.6 nW, larger GBW (12.7 kHz), lower PM (61.7 deg) and a slightly larger A_{vo} (61.7 dB). The above results are within the range determined by corner and MC analyses.

Fig.8. Measured open-loop frequency characteristics of OTA, $C_L=20\text{pF}$.

Fig.9 Measured GBW, PM and Avo against the input common-mode voltage,, $C_L=20pF$.

Fig. 9. shows the GBW, PM and A_{vo} variations against the input common-mode voltage (V_{icm}). The results prove low sensitivity of the presented structure to V_{icm} variations over a wide range of input voltages, approaching supply rails. Notably, the DC voltage gain remained above 48 dB for V_{icm} ranging from 50 mV to 250 mV, confirming stability and robustness of the design.

Figs. 10 and 11 show transient responses of OTA in a voltage follower configuration, for a $300mV_{pp}$ input square and sine waves respectively. Note, that the phase of the input signal has been reversed for better visibility.

Fig.10. Square-wave response of OTA in a voltage follower configuration with $C_L=20pF$, X axis: $200\mu s/div$, Y axis $50 mV/div$.

Fig.11 Sine-wave response of OTA in a voltage follower configuration for 300 mV_{pp}/10Hz, X axis: 20ms/div, Y axis 50 mV/div.

The total harmonic distortion (THD) of the OTA configured as a voltage follower, against V_{in} , for $f=10$ Hz, is shown in Fig. 12, where the THD of the used signal generator is also shown for comparison. The THD increases with frequency. For instance, for $V_{in}=290$ mV_{pp} the THD was equal to 0.86% for $f=10$ Hz, 0.86% for 100Hz and 1.51% for $f=1$ kHz.

Fig.12. THD against V_{in} in a VF configuration, $f=10$ Hz.

Fig.13. shows the simulated noise characteristic of OTA for $I_B=4$ nA and nominal process parameters. The input referred thermal noise was about $4.6 \mu\text{V}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$, while the flicker noise corner frequency was 10 Hz only.

Fig. 13. Simulated input-referred noise of the OTA for nominal conditions.

Table VI. Measured parameters of OTA, $I_B=4\text{nA}$, $V_{DD}=0.3\text{V}$, $C_L=20\text{pF}$.

Parameter	value	Parameter	value
A_{vo}	61.7 dB	SR_+	3.4 V/ms
GBW	12.7 kHz	SR_-	26 V/ms
PM	61.7 °	1 % t_{sett+}/t_{sett-}	170/170 µs
CMRR	96.9 dB	THD ^a	0.86/1.51 %
PSRR	57.4 dB	P_{diss}	23.6 nW
Input offset	6.51 mV	Area	2480 µm ²

a) For $V_{in}=290\text{mV}_{pp}$, 100Hz/1kHz

The measured parameters of OTA are summarized in Table VI. Across five additional measured samples, the maximum observed deviations, with respect to Table VI, were 0.85 dB for A_{vo} , 0.41 kHz for GBW, and 2.2° for PM.

Table VII shows a comparison of the proposed OTA with state of the art designs published in recent years. In order to better compare their performance, the standard figures of merit have been used: $FOM_S=GBW \times C_L/P_{diss}$, $FOM_L=SR \times C_L/P_{diss}$, where SR is the average slew-rate.

The OTAs in Table VII can be categorized into three types: full-custom (FC), inverter-based (INV) and so-called digital OTAs (DIG). Notably, the digital OTAs achieve the best FOMs, significantly outperforming all other designs. However, they operate with relatively large C_L , which establishes a dominant pole used for frequency compensation. Moreover, this new technique shows the highest THD, is highly sensitive to PVT variations, and, while promising, requires further study and development [1].

TABLE VII. Performance comparison of selected experimentally tested ULV OTAs.

Parameter	This work	[12] 2023	[11] 2023	[10] 2022	[14] 2022	[17] 2021	[16] 2021	[9] 2020	[8] 2020	[7] 2020	[6] 2018	[4] 2015	[3] 2014
Technology, [nm]	65	65	130	180	65	180	180	65	180	180	180	65	130
Operation mode	FC	FC	FC	FC	INV	DIG	DIG	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
V _{DD} , [V]	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.25	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.35	0.25
C _L , [pF]	20	50	35	2x15	0.5	80	150	15	30	30	20	3	15
DC gain, [dB]	61.7	38	86.8	60	64	30	73	70	98.1	>64.7	>65.8	43	60
GBW, [kHz]	12.7	1650	10.3	7.0	6850	4	60	9.5	3.1	2.96	2.78	3.6k	1.88
Phase margin, [°]	61.7	70.3	58.3	60.2 ^b	62	54	-	88	54	52	61	56	52.5
SR+, [V/ms]	3.4	250	2.5	78	1510	0.2	19	2.0	14	1.9	6.44	5.6k	0.64
SR-, [V/ms]	26	110	5.0	80	1510	0.2	19	2.0	4.2	6.4	7.80	5.6k	0.77
CMRR @ DC, [dB]	96.9	39.8	57.8	85.4	-	-	65	62.5	60	110	72	46	-
PSRR @ DC, [dB]	57.4	44.7	46.6	76.3	-	-	50	38	61	56	62	35	-
THD [%]	0.2 ^c	-	0.36 ^d	-	-	1.26-2.82 ^e	2.0 ^f	-	0.49 ^g	1 ^h	0.08 ⁱ	0.6	0.2 ^j
Thermal noise, [μV/Hz ^{1/2}]	4.6 ^b	0.25	2.86	0.39	-	-	-	-	1.8 ^b	1.6 ^b	1.85 ^b	-	3.3
Power, [nW]	23.6	2550	33.7	24	875	1	108	26	13	12.6	15.4	17e3	18
FOM _S , [MHz · pF/μW]	10.76	32.35	10.68	8.75	3.91	598	80.2	5.481	7.154	7.047	3.61	0.634	1.568
FOM _L , [V · pF/μs · μW]	12.46	3.53	3.86	98.7	0.86	28.96	26.5	1.154	21.0	9.880	9.30	0.989	0.584
Silicon area, [mm ²] $\times 10^{-3}$	2.48	1.1	2.34	7.9	0.2	1.0	1.0	2.0	9.8	8.5	8.2	5.0	83

b) simulated value, c) at 200mV_{pp}/100Hz, d) at 200mV_{pp}/100 Hz, e) min and max value for measured samples at 50mV_p/3Hz, f) at 50mV_p/2.5Hz, g) at 250mV_{pp}/10Hz, h) at 255mV_{pp}, i) at 250mV/10Hz, j) at 150mV_{pp}/10Hz

Full custom designs ensure the best reliability, and hence repeatability of parameters under PVT variations, which is obtained thanks to the well-defined bias points [1]. Among the FC designs, the proposed OTA offers one of the best FOMs, with only one design, [12], surpassing it in terms of the small-signal FOM_S. However, it was achieved with larger C_L. The OTA in [12], which also uses a PPF and a current buffer compensation, but without a second loop, can operate with large capacitances, but its minimum C_L is limited to 5pF. In contrast, the proposed OTA remains stable even with C_L=0, and provides much higher voltage gain, CMRR and PSRR. In addition, this work demonstrates for the first time that the

combination of partial positive feedback and current buffer compensation significantly reduces sensitivity to mismatch in PPF-based structures.

Regarding the large-signal FOM_L , the two designs [8] and [10] achieve larger values, however, they were implemented in 0.18 μm technology with significantly larger g_{mb}/g_m ratio, that results in larger output current of their input stages for the same input step. Moreover, the OTA in [10] is supplied with larger V_{DD} , that allows for larger amplitude of the input step, that for input stages with expansive type transfer characteristic (like for most of the OTAs in Table VI, including the proposed one), also results in larger SR.

Considering the DC voltage gain, only one 65-nm OTA, [9], achieves a slightly higher value, but its power efficiency, as indicated by standard FOMs, is lower. The OTA proposed in this work shows the highest input referred noise, however, this is caused by a low g_{mb}/g_m ratio for the used technology, which for transistors M_1 is equal to about 0.21 at the operating point, about two times less than for example for designs [6] - [8], realized in 0.18 μm technology, that increases the input noise in the same proportion.

It is also worth pointing out the high value of the CMRR parameter of the designed OTA. Only one design [7] offers larger CMRR, but it was implemented using a 180-nm technology, with larger intrinsic voltage gains of MOS transistors.

5. Conclusion

This work presents a new ULV OTA implemented in 65 nm technology. It was shown that the integration of the PPF technique with the hybrid frequency compensation method significantly reduces the sensitivity of the GBW and PM to transistor mismatch. This improvement enhances stability and allows for an increased depth of positive feedback, resulting in a higher voltage gain of the OTA. Measured results confirmed the theory and competitive performance of the OTA, compared to state of the art. The designed OTA shows a DC voltage gain of 61.7 dB, with a GBW of 12.7 kHz at 20-pF load, while consumes only a 23.7 nW of power. The standard FoMs for the design were 10.8 MHz·pF/ μW and 12.5 V·pF/ μW , one of the best among full custom ULV OTAs.

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